

ROLE OF INSURANCE COMPANIES IN PROJECT FINANCING THROUGH CAPITAL MARKET

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In the effective implementation of economic reforms in our country, it is important to organize innovative development, create a healthy investment environment, and attract institutional investors, especially, insurance companies to the economy. In this process, it is necessary to attract insurance companies not only to the real sector, but also to the capital market, to create the necessary conditions for their investment, and to develop the capital market by ensuring the participation of insurance companies. Insurance companies are active in the capital market in order to effectively use their financial resources, expand their activities, and especially maximize profits in global stock market. As a result of increasing the activity of insurance companies in the capital market, it is possible to develop the local capital market, effectively use free funds, increase investment attractiveness, and develop local enterprises as well as financing projects. It is necessary to develop the local capital market and increase the activity of institutional investors based on the study of the activities of institutional investors in the capital market of developed and developing countries. By attracting foreign institutional investors, it is possible to develop the capital market in our country, ensure the introduction of new techniques and technologies, develop the infrastructure of the capital market, and increase the activity of institutional investors in the capital market. Therefore, participation of insurance companies in project financing through securities becomes urgent.

If we pay attention to the participation of insurance companies in the capital market of our country, we can say that the indicators of insurance companies indicate that there are a number of issues that need to be resolved in the capital market. In particular, if we study the results of the participation of institutional investors in the trading operations of RFB "Tashkent", we can see that banks, insurance companies, etc. are the main participants (Table 1). Table 1 shows the results of the participation of institutional investors in trade operations at RFB "Tashkent", according to which insurance companies bought securities of banks worth 5933.9 million soums. Moreover, insurance companies bought securities worth 1,754.6 million soums of state-owned companies. Other companies bought securities of banks worth 6535.3 million soums, securities of insurance companies worth 10159.7 million soums.

Table 1

Analysis of the participation of insurance companies in the trading operations of RFB "Tashkent" (as of February 1, 2022)¹

№	Investors in a short position	Investors in the buying position (million soums)		
		Individual	Insurance Companies	Other Companies
1.	Banks	1500,2	5933,9	6535,3
2.	State, local government or foreign organizations	-	-	32607,1
3.	Individual investors	13485,7	10,4	700,6
4.	Insurance companies	1,7	-	10159,7
5.	Other companies	4836,6	-	-
6.	Companies with a state share	-	1754,6	-

It is necessary to analyze the profitability of the shares of institutional investors and other joint-stock companies participating in our local capital market in order to attract free money in the hands of the population to the capital market, create conditions for the active participation of local and foreign investors in the capital market, and thereby develop the capital market.

Figure 1 shows the volume of transactions with securities at RFB "Tashkent" over the years, from 0.3 trillion soums in 2017 to 4.8 trillion soums in 2022. The significant increase of this indicator in recent years is due to the fact that public offering of stocks is organized in the national practice and due to the implemented measures.

Figure 1. The volume of transactions with securities at RFB "Tashkent" (trln. soums)²

¹ <https://www.uzse.uz/abouts/uzstatistics>

² <https://deponet.uz/uz/page/kimmatli-kogozlar-markaziy-depozitariysi-davlat-korhonasining-2022-yil-davomidagi-faoliyati>

The following conclusions were formed in the study of participation of insurance companies through capital market in project financing. In order to develop the participation of insurance companies in project financing through securities, we believe that it is appropriate to focus on attracting foreign institutional investors, especially, insurance companies, as investors and financial intermediaries. Therefore, it is necessary to create conditions for foreign insurance companies and investment intermediaries, to participate in the local capital market. In particular, it is necessary to provide insurance companies and investment intermediaries with the opportunity to carry out securities underwriting activities without obtaining a license. In this case, it is necessary to develop special requirements and criteria for foreign insurance companies and investment intermediaries to carry out securities underwriting activities without obtaining a license.